

THE ROLE AND PECULIARITIES OF UZBEK CHILDREN'S LITERATURE

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Abstract:

In this article, using the analytical and synthetic structuralize method, using the examples of Orient literature, we consider the specifics of children's literature in the light of genre classification, due to a special type of literary target layer of the reader. We consider them in terms of themes, motives and selection of literary characters.

Key words: children's literature, culture, oral creativity, didactic literature, folk didactics.

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Children's literature is distinguished by the difficult task of educating the future generation physically strong, spiritually pure, mentally healthy, intellectually, spiritually, courageously, patriotically. A characteristic feature of this literature is that it is a variable phenomenon, which is directly related to the reader's age, historical period and environment children show its simplicity and the dominance of action and characters.

Nowadays, presents the function of standard literary works in shaping children's ethical values, as an effort to shape children's proper character. This learn about is library research blended with descriptive-qualitative evaluation techniques. The records collection methods used include documentation and reference digging to explore the moral values contained in usual literary, in order to structure a child's desirable character.

Children's literature is a vital part of the literature of all international locations due to the fact it shapes the minds and worldviews of future generations. The culture of creating a specific literature for teenagers is manifested in the structure of a vital spiritual want of society's development. Although Uzbek kid's literature has come into existence in the written literature of the East on the basis of works labeled with the aid of such names as "pandnom", "mavizatnama", "nasihatnama", "moral books", etc., it is diagnosed that its formation is intently related to enlightenment – reforms of the school-educational device. [1]

In the improvement of Uzbek kid's literature, first of all, social reality, then folks' oral creativity, didactic literature, and classical children's reading are regarded as important phenomena. Children's literature, which seemed in Uzbek literature in the context of the revolutions of the Enlightenment, countrywide renaissance, and modernist literature, is a unique and uncommon direction, which first regarded as a phenomenon, a revolution, and then developed as an impartial science. The formation of children's literature among almost all peoples is closely connected with education and the reform of the school system. The stabilization of Uzbek children's literature dates back to the enlightenment

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movement of the second half of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century. Saidrasul Azizi, Munavvarkori, Abdulla Avloni, Khamza and dozens of other educators created about fifty alphabets and books for reading for students of Uzbek schools according to the “new method” (“usulijadidiya”), are the roof of Uzbek children's literature, are vivid examples of value.

Children's reading was created on the basis of society's understanding of the rights of its children and understanding them as their own heirs. Before the advent of written literature, it acted in the form of folk didactics – ethno pedagogy [2]. However, in search of the affirmation of the Islamic faith, it embarked on a religious and ethical path and became sanctified, having acquired a true religious essence. For this reason, they started in the past, and then paid special attention to understanding, accepting and turning its content and ideas at the level of the foundations of faith into a criterion for practical activity. Based on this logic, the content of Uzbek children's reading in the past was formed. The influence of the Holy Quran and Hadith played a decisive role in this. For this reason, it has been stipulated in all Islamic countries that the basic idea of any kind of work must be taken from the Qur'an or Hadith. Since then, religion has become the main means of morality and education. The need for artistic interpretation and interpretation of the sacred verses of the Koran and hadiths gave rise to a number of religious and moral works of a didactic nature in classical literature. This, in turn, constitutes a separate stage and direction in the history of Uzbek classical literature called didactic literature.

The works of Uzbek children's reading according to their purpose can be divided into two main categories:

In the first category, as mentioned above, popular classical advice, religious and ethical instructions and instructions, adapted to the pedagogical thinking of the people and mostly written in the form of advice to children, mainly express the life and moral experience of children. Adults from their language, taste and point of view, the second category includes works of a scientific and educational (cognitive) orientation, some of which are popular, and some are adapted to the age, taste and level of children. In addition, children's fiction works as part of children's reading due to the fact that it is intended to be read by children. These three processes, becoming a single stream, constitute the content of children's reading and ensure its continuity.

Into second category, Genre characteristics of children's literature Specific characteristics of children's literature. For children, as well as for adults, creativity is possible on all topics related to people, society and nature. At the heart of this commonality of children's and adult literature lies a feature that clarifies the difference between them. For example, while children are forbidden to read works that express the complex aspects of adult life, children are encouraged to read the works of the poetic literary fairy tale "Qo'ng'izoy bilan sichqonboy" by K. Muhammadi, written in children's language. way on the same topic. The fact is that children's literature as a form of social consciousness expresses children's views on being, and in assessing events - its own characteristics, that is, the aesthetic attitude of the modern generation to being [3].

Conclusion

Children's literature is a vital part of typical literature, it has its personal characteristics, is focused on the interests of reader-children and is therefore uncommon by means of its creative originality, which corresponds to the psychology of children. Functional kinds of kid's literature encompass

educational, cognitive, moral, and leisure works. Children's literature is phrase artwork as section of universal literature. Children's literature is a fundamental section of prevalent literature, it has its very own characteristics, is targeted on the pursuits of reader-children and is therefore distinct via its inventive originality, which corresponds to the psychology of children. Functional kinds of kid's literature include educational, cognitive, moral, and enjoyment works. Children's literature is word art as phase of ordinary literature.

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